

Strategies for Female Talent Management

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Abstract

There are some factors that are common among women who have been successful in their profession. While it is true that many of these factors are also needed for men in the Job, Women experience their career journey differently due to differences in the way in which they are socialized, the roles they play, often unconscious bias held by both men and women, and the still prevalent masculine cultures of many organizations. This paper will introduce the key points relevant to retain female talent and harnessing the power of them. It explicitly talks about the strategies for finding and keeping female talent, and to advancing women in the workplace. This paper solidly explains the solutions, norms, and practices of attracting and retaining female talent. It ensures women to attain better representation in leadership roles.

Keywords: Female talent, Mentoring program, Career progression, Gender diversity, Mentors, Reverse mentoring, Buddy system, Company culture, Work-life balance, Promoting leadership.

Introduction

Women often have a sense that they are outside of the mainstream but do not understand the problems impacting their career journey. If they had clarity on the barriers they face, they would be in a better position to overcome them. Gender diversity programs are all about addressing an uneven playing field that is not providing equal career development opportunities for all. It is important to realize that this uneven playing field is not created consciously or out of malice or overt discrimination. Efforts should be undertaken to ensure that women are visible in organization practice committees, industry trade associations, business development campaigns, and strategic client assignments. Diverse approaches to leadership, business development, career–life integration and career navigation is an effective strategy to support and nurture the aspirations of emerging female leaders.

STRATEGIES FOR FINDING FEMALE TALEN

Focus on career progression: Women today expect more from their careers than any previous generation. Among the women we surveyed, female millennial (born 1980-1995) and women just starting their careers said career advancement was the most attractive trait in an employer. The least attractive was a lack of opportunities. Companies that establish formal career progression plans will have better luck in attracting employees and keeping them motivated and committed.

Revisit people policies: All companies could benefit from taking a hard look at their policies and assessing which ones meet the needs of female employees. These could include leadership opportunities, professional development, global mobility, flexibility, and career progression. Proactive organizations will make sure programmes are updated and new ones put into place. There are many of them: 28% of employers have already adopted a formal returner programme, and a further 25% are currently exploring this opportunity.

Mindset matters: Globally, 30% of women said that employers do too little to treat women equally in the workplace. In a survey of professional women, more than one in five women reported personal experience of gender discrimination when applying or interviewing for a job. Additionally, the global study suggested that there is a significant disconnect between the views of women and employers on the barriers to hire more women.

Diversity should be baked in and shared: The good news is that 76% of employers have incorporated diversity and inclusion in their employer brands. Among companies with more than 10,000 employees, 88% report having done so. But talking about diversity is no longer enough. Demonstrable progress such as an inclusive workplace culture and high levels of collaboration, feedback, and care is increasingly important to women when deciding where to work.

Last but not least, lead by example: Leaders have a vital role to play, by creating the right tone at the top, inspiring other women and helping them to reach their full potential. A diversified leadership team is important, as is an inclusive workplace culture that brings everyone to the table. This means that conversations about inclusion should be carried out by men as well as women, and all senior employees should be strongly encouraged to mentor and build trusting relationships with people. (Moritz & Karve. 2017).

STRATEGIES FOR ADVANCING WOMEN IN THE WORKPLACE

Create new opportunities: Companies need to think differently about how to create new opportunities for women who aspire to lead. Rather than wait for a man to step down from the company's board of directors to add a woman, increase the total number of board seats to accommodate a new female director.

Encourage mentors and sponsorships: Mentors and sponsors are beneficial for personal and career growth. Companies can encourage women to find mentors and sponsors to help them develop their skills and build their career paths. Mentors can help employees think about their career growth, while sponsors can help make it happen.

Provide a network of support: Companies can create advisory boards to enhance career opportunities for women and drive local and national initiatives that support, advance, retain and reward women.

Measure progress: Companies can track various inclusion and diversity-specific performance indicators, such as talent acquisition, attrition, career progression, and leadership. Leadership can review this information to help senior leaders and their direct reports that will move the high-performing women they have identified by name forward. Companies can also provide

feedback at the individual level to reinforce high performance.

Invest in the future: Millennial represent the most educated generation of women in history. They are very socially conscious and consider a company's purpose and commitment to corporate citizenship as top priorities. Connecting with this generation of talented women requires understanding their values, communicating the company's goal, and engaging them in the company's social mission. (Doughtie. 2017).

WAYS TO GET WOMEN INTO LEADERSHIP POSITIONS

Having a diverse workforce, like improved operational and financial performance, increased innovation, and enhanced company reputation, organizations are still struggling to attract and retain women in leadership roles. It's not easy developing strategies that encourage women to climb the corporate ladder.

Reverse Mentoring: Reverse mentoring, also called reciprocal mentoring, is an outstanding example of how to create visibility of up-and-coming female leaders to top executives, as well as expose female leaders to the most strategic work at the company. While the method is informal, it helps break down some of the unconscious bias.

Encouraging Self-Care: Multinational Oil Company Chevron offers full-fitness and self-care facilities onsite at their global locations. Employees have the opportunity to take care of themselves by working out during the day and getting massages or facials without having to leave their worksite. This enables women to find balance and stay healthy.

The Buddy System: The company matches senior leaders to rise female talent for one to two years. The objectives are to build confidence, create visibility of talent internally, and provide access to stretch assignments. What makes Deloitte's program successful is that the company measures the results of the coaching efforts and holds each coach accountable for the success of his assigned leader in developing new capabilities, and expansions of networks.

Flexible Work Schedules: Global health care company Roche has a unique flexible work program, offering employees 12 days of remote work per quarter, which comes to 48 days a year. If an employee needs to stay home to be with kids or sick parents or to focus on a specific project, the company trusts that they will still get their work done.

Transparent and Collaborative Career Mapping: Development plans, stretch assignments, promotions, and networking opportunities are equal for men and women who have rated with similar capabilities. This structure removes the chances of women not being aware of opportunities for their development at higher levels, and it creates visibility to top leadership. Annual reviews are used by the Talent Development team to ensure women are recognized by leadership and for selection in highly visible programs.

Unique Family Support: Pharmaceutical company Eli Lilly offers after - school programs like science camps, math sessions, and other activities in the evening. These innovative programs enable employees with families to retain demanding positions without the worry of leaving children at home, which helps to reduce the choice women often must make between family and work. (Stuckey n.d).

RETAIN FEMALE TALENT

Start a Formal Mentoring Program: People tend to network and develop mentorships with people of their gender. If men have more opportunity for leadership roles and they network with other men, men will continue to dominate leadership roles. Women, who have mentors with less clout and are sponsored, need access to mentors and sponsors of both genders.

Institute Flexible Work Arrangements: Set standards for both genders and give managers the training they need to be comfortable in managing flextime workers. This removes the barrier for women who are the primary caretakers in their family, which is a significant amount, according to the Bureau of Labor Statistics. It reports women do 54 percent more of childcare than men, and 50 percent of elder-care.

Function as a Results-Only Work Environment: The traditional solution to work-life challenges is the decision to have women stay home. This reinforces gender inequality, and subtly disadvantages women, particularly mothers. Judging women by the quality of their work rather than whether or not they are physically present can increase retention. (Loehr. 2017)

BEST PRACTICES FOR ATTRACTING FEMALE TALENT

Understand How Female Talent Looks for New Job Opportunities

Some research suggests that women are more likely to use job reviews and rely on personal relationships to find employer information as well as secure new jobs. They are less likely than men to use certain mainstream recruiting sites, which makes female talent more difficult to reach.

Broadcast Your Benefits, Culture & Policies

Most employees value transparency, but there are certain benefits and cultural issues in particular that are stigmatizing. Therefore, don't make women by asking to choose between getting information about things like work flexibility, maternity leave, and having to face the potential stigma.

Examine Your Pay Practices

Women in the workplace tell us they are very aware of and concerned about the gender pay gap. Even if you cannot commit to a full-fledged compensation audit across your entire firm, should set practices into place that encourage consistent compensation across job titles.

Prioritize Gender Diversity, Particularly among Management

Fairygodboss data proves that there is a clear correlation between women's job satisfaction and diverse management teams. In other words, this management ranks are essential to show that a company takes gender equality seriously.

Ensure the Company is Promoting Women Fairly

According to Fairygodboss members, unequal promotion is the top area in which they observe gender inequity in their organizations. Some of the reasons behind this concern are expressed as unequal access to sponsors, unfair evaluation standards, and boys' club mentality among leadership.

Formalize Flexibility & Work-Life Balance Policies

A well-articulated flexibility policy can be a real asset to employers looking to recruit the best talent interested in clarity about whether they can achieve the work-life balance they want.

Encourage Mentorship & Sponsorship of Women

Women consistently report less access to senior leadership. Consider formal programs or other options to build an infrastructure to support, mentor and sponsor women at your company.

Lead the Way With Bold Steps

Companies are making a change by demanding greater diversity from their vendors, performing compensation audits and engaging in unconscious bias. The leadership stance on gender diversity issues can make a difference not just to employees, but to the employer brand.

Engage Men as Allies & Draw them into the Conversation

Although most men support gender diversity in the workplace, they are often unaware of bias or discrimination when it takes place. More direct and honest conversations between men and their female peers and direct reports can lead to greater sensitivity, and more effective partnership. Direct Employers Association Guest. (2017).

Company Culture

- **Ensuring that everyone has a voice:** Something that may hold women back is not having the confidence to speak up. In certain situations, some people may not feel comfortable sharing their ideas, no matter how good they may be. Make sure that these people are not only heard but also listened by the management.
- **Look beyond the usual perks:** The company culture isn't just about what company perks offer the employees, it should be aligned with the goals and values of the company. Equality and work-life balance should be at the core of the culture, offering value for everyone involved.

Work-Life Balance

- **Flexible working practices:** Flexible working has been shown to help all employees, not just women or those with children. Flexible working can work to both the employers and employees advantage. It does however make switching off from work much harder and this needs to be taken into consideration.
- **Part-time work:** Offering the potential for working part - time can be beneficial to your existing employees, particularly those returning to work from maternity leave. Allowing the balance between home life and a full-time job with a happy medium that can work well for both parties.

Promoting Leadership

- **Provide professional opportunities for promotion:** promotions to leadership or senior roles should be done on merit of skill, not length of service. The mentality of length of service promotion can sometimes prevent women progressing in business. By promoting on an individual's skills, it allows to play for all potential successors.
- **Assigning a mentor to women:** Mentors can offer another level of support for women who can be invaluable to their development and progression at work. In addition to the support they offer, a mentor will coach and give much needed advice to these women, meaning they are better equipped to progress and offer more to the business. (Edgoose. 2018).

Tailor Your Interviews

Men are more likely to overstate their experience and capabilities, women will understate theirs. With this in mind, the candidate interviews should focus on evidence and proof of abilities. Pay special attention to previous references over candidate's self-promotion. Enlist at least one female staff member into the interview process, to help to understand female candidates as much as possible.

Introduce External Networking and Mentoring

Countless non-profit organizations and networks exist with the sole purpose of inspiring female leadership, holding conferences and events that businesses, and employees can attend. Networking with high profile women, either in a specific business sector or more generally, can be all the inspiration female staff need.

Incentivize Joint Paternity Leave

Most companies do not realize, that maternity leave can be split 50-50 between mother and father. Most parents are eligible for Shared Parental Leave, and Statutory Shared Parental Pay, which means the care of the child, does not have to be taken just by the female, or one parent, and can be split into different blocks and shared by both parties. (Dawson. 2018).

SOLUTIONS AND STRATEGIES FOR FEMALE TALENT

The organization makes good business sense. It creates a stronger pipeline of future leaders by accessing all the talent that's out there and perhaps more importantly, a balanced senior team brings a diversity of perspectives, experience and leadership styles to the table. Supporting female talent is now firmly on the talent management agenda.

Gather Data about the Current Situation

Gathering accurate data about the current situation can help the organization to secure support and buy-in for your plans. It will also provide with the evidence, to build a strong business case, to help the organization support, and retain female talent. Once getting some quantitative data, the next step is to supplement this with information gathered directly from employees about their experiences.

Get Senior Management Buy-In

The senior team in the organization must be committed to supporting female talent in the right way. This is about demonstrating genuine support, and walking the talk wherever possible. Tone at the top is important, therefore the organization's board, top leaders and management team should be actively involved with, committed to, and accountable for gender diversity.

Increase Accountability for Gender Diversity

Setting gender diversity targets, and making leaders and managers across your organization accountable for recruiting, developing and promoting women are proven ways of improving gender diversity. Managers across all levels and regions were asked to regularly report on the diversity of their talent. They must also show the specific steps they are taking to develop employees by providing mentors, coaching, networking opportunities and development programmes tailored to the needs of women in particular.

Develop Mentoring Programmes for Women

Mentoring has shown to be important for women because they often have difficulty in building social capital at work. Setting up a formal mentoring programme to help women advance their careers is an essential step. The more accepted mentoring is in the organization, the easier it will be for women to get involved.

Promote Flexible Working - for Everyone

If organization can offer employees flexible working arrangements, then the organization will be better placed to retain valuable talent, and create a balanced workforce. Some organizations offer flexibility to all employees, as a way of increasing engagement and productivity across the workforce. (Scott, S. 2016, March 4).

Conclusion

Women experience their career journey different due to differences in the way in which they are socialized. The roles in society that women often play, unconscious bias in business held by both men, and women, and the still prevalent masculine cultures of many organizations. Best practice of gender diversity programs are about addressing an uneven playing field that is not providing equal career development opportunities for all. The uneven job is not intentional and is often invisible. It is important to realize that this uneven place is not created consciously, or out of malice, or overt discrimination. Therefore Constant efforts must be taken to fill the gap and strategies be framed to encourage female talent.

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